

XR5.0

Human-Centric AI-Enabled Extended Reality
Applications for the Industry 5.0 Era

XR5.0 TECHNOLOGIES FOR WORKER-CENTRIC AIRCRAFT MAINTENANCE TRAINING

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the XR5.0 pilot application for worker-centric aircraft maintenance training, focusing on the maintenance process of the Wing Anti-Ice Valve (WAIV). To address industry challenges such as workforce shortages, increasing system complexity, and strict safety regulations, the proposed solution integrates extended reality, artificial intelligence and digital twin technologies to enhance the effectiveness and resilience of aircraft maintenance technician training. Two use cases were developed. The first use case is based on mixed reality for on-the-job virtual training with adaptive guidance and performance monitoring, and the second use case is based on a virtual reality application for off-the-job digital twin guidance. The architecture for the uses cases combines immersive 3D visualization, AI-assisted procedural support, real-time analytics, and stress monitoring via wearables. A preliminary evaluation was conducted with junior and senior technicians that demonstrated high usability, strong perceived training value, low cognitive workload, and positive acceptance of AI-supported guidance. Despite connectivity constraints, results indicate that XR5.0 provides a feasible and promising approach to improving maintenance training quality and operational readiness.

SECTION 1. INTRODUCTION

The air transportation industry faces significant challenges in maintaining high safety standards while managing increasing aircraft system complexity. These challenges are further exacerbated by a shortage of qualified aircraft maintenance technicians (AMTs), many in advanced age as reported by the Aeronautical Repair Station Association [1]. These factors highlight the need for innovative, scalable training solutions to ensure workforce readiness and regulatory compliance.

A critical subsystem within the Minimum Equipment List is the Wing Anti-Ice Valve (WAIV), whose proper functioning is essential for safe aircraft operations. WAIV failures can result in prolonged aircraft grounding and require specialized maintenance procedures, demanding high levels of technical competence.

The XR5.0 project addresses this need by delivering an interactive XR training environment for WAIV maintenance. The platform enables AMTs to conduct each step of the disassembly process within a realistic 3D simulation, offering structured guidance on safety measures, tool selection, and procedural workflows. Training content is personalized based on user experience and performance metrics, such as execution time and errors.

By combining immersive visualization and 3D interaction that replicates real-world motor tasks, XR5.0 enhances procedural understanding, skill acquisition and confidence [2,3]. The overall objective is to improve the effectiveness, reliability, and resilience of training for junior AMTs.

SECTION 2. XR5.0 PILOT APPLICATION

The pilot addresses the maintenance of a critical aircraft subsystem, the WAIV, through two complementary use cases.

UC1 - Virtual Training

The first use case is named as Virtual Training and focuses on on-the-job training through a mixed reality environment based on the XR5.0 Training Platform and AI tools, supporting junior AMTs during maintenance procedures with contextual guidance, adaptive feedback, and performance monitoring (Figure 1-3).

The following images depict the training environment used to address each of the user stories derived from the co-creation activities of the project.

Figure 1. Which are the safety measures?

Figure 2. How to access the WAIV device in the aircraft?

Figure 3. How to access the WAIV device?

UC2 - AMT Digital Twin

The second use case relates to the AMT Digital Twin. This use case focuses on off-the-job training through a VR environment leveraging the XR5.0 Human Digital Twin, enabling immersive rehearsal of maintenance tasks, procedural understanding, and skill acquisition in a safe and controlled setting (Figure 4-6).

Figure 4. How to access the WAIV device?

Figure 5. Which are the tools to use?

Figure 6. In what order should I disassemble the WAIV?

Architecture

The pilot's prototype integrates several key technical components, including AI-assisted XR training environments, human digital twins (HDT), immersive VR/AR instructional content, real-time performance feedback mechanisms, and stress monitoring via wearable sensors. The diagram depicting the logical view and the different components is show below in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Pilot architecture

Components

The following table (Table 1). describes the technical components involved in the applications for these use cases.

Table 1. Description of the technical components.

Technical Components	Description
Workers' data collection & analytics	Continuous heart rate monitoring to detect stress levels and enable training adaptation.
Workers' digital twins	Shadowing (shadow operator) that will guide the user through the correct procedure.
Personalized XR content development	Customization according to the user's experience level.
Adaptation of personalized XR content	Real-time adaptation of the VR panels according to user's activation level.
XR-enabled AL & NSAI models	Real-time object recognition to help the operator identifying valve components.
Generative AI models	Answers to user queries based on the training materials.

Training material	XR-based content based on traditional materials: equipment and safety checklists, access and procedure workflows.
Cloud-based XR training asset repository	Cloud-based repositior to store the XR training materials.
Hololight Hub	Remote access to the XR app through streaming.
Training programs	Removal and installation programs for the WAIV.

SECTION 3. EVALUATION

The evaluation was conducted in the TAP premises in Lisbon Portugal. The evaluation was performed in a hangar in TAP where two participants were recruited that were AMT at TAP, one junior and a senior AMT. Before starting the session, written informed consent was provided by the participants describing the purpose of the task and the evaluation procedures. The session started with preparing the setup, VR preparation, and App activity metrics by attaching the smartwatch in the wrist of the participant and connecting the App activity metrics. For the second use case, the HDT was not provided yet as this is an early stage of development. The XR task started by asking the participants to explore the app and follow the steps of each training environment. The instructions were done verbally and feedback was also continuously collected during the session through notes taken by the experimenter. At the end of the procedure, the participants filled in the evaluation form available on Google forms. The overall procedure took about 45 minutes for each participant.

The following figure (Figure 8) depicts the validation scenario.

Figure 8. Validation scenario

The evaluation infrastructure was the following:

- Shopfloor at TAP. The aircraft and WAIV device were not available at the time of the evaluation.
- 3D models of the aircraft and WAIV device

Hardware:

- Meta Quest 3 XR device
- Pixel Watch 2

Software:

- Unity-based XR Virtual Training / HDT Application
- Hololight Stream
- XR-enabled AI Assistant
- Activity Metrics App (Smartwatch Connector Wear OS)
- XR5.0 Clawdite Platform (workers' digital twins)

Validation Scenario

The validation scenario consisted of the two use cases described above. The first use case “Virtual Training” consisted of having the AMT exploring the application and follow the steps of each training environment. As the aircraft equipped with the WAIV was not available, the training could not be fully executed. However, participants were asked to explore the application and follow the procedural steps while using the different features of the app, namely the AI assistant, the 3D model explorer, and the interactive panels, in order to assess the usability of the XR environment. For the second use case “AMT Digital Twin”, given that the shadowing operator was not yet available at the time of this test, the task focused on exploring the application and the different features of the environment. One activity involved selecting the correct tools required to carry out the procedure on the WAIV. Accordingly, participants were asked to assess the tools used in this use case and to understand the overall workflow of the activity. The experiment began with the first use case being assessed by both participants, followed by the second use case.

SECTION 4. RESULTS

The technical and industrial evaluation for the early prototype of the XR5.0 training solution for aircraft maintenance was focused mainly in the first use case “Virtual Training” with a specific focus on the WAIV procedure. The evaluation focused on the technical performance, user experience, usability, and task load and human-centric aspects, but also on the evaluation by each technical component. Data collection relied on structured post-session questionnaires combining Likert-scale ratings (1-5) and qualitative feedback.

Technical Performance

The XR application demonstrated good stability and responsiveness (rating = 4), with no crashes or major disruptions during the session. Visual and interaction quality received very high ratings (4.5). Hardware setup achieved the maximum rating (5), indicating minimal configuration effort even for users without prior XR experience. The overall technical performance score was 4.5. One exception was the Hololight Stream cloud integration, which could not be fully tested due to connectivity limitations in the aircraft hangar. A standalone

mode was used for testing. This highlights deployment challenges in large industrial environments.

Usability and User Experience

Usability and user experience were rated highly (overall 4.5). Participants reported strong comfort and confidence when using the XR device (5), and the interface was considered intuitive and easy to navigate (4,5). A slightly reduced the score was obtained for behavioural consistency (4). Trust in system responses was also high (4.5). Qualitative feedback confirmed the results above that immersive 3D visualization significantly enhanced spatial understanding, i.e., “*The diversity of available panels.*” Or “*The visualization of units and components in three dimensions without losing awareness of the surrounding environment, along with the wide range of tools and systems available to the operator.*”

Work Impact and Effectiveness

The perceived operational value of the XR solution was particularly high. Participants reported maximum ratings (5) for improved understanding of WAIV procedures and increased confidence and motivation. Efficiency improvement and workplace safety potential were highly rated (4.5). The ability to perform tasks independently received a slightly lower score (4). The XR-based training environment was considered as a good option for enabling safe, risk-free practice (5). The overall assessment in this dimension was 4.5.

Task Load and Human-Centric Aspects

The Task Load Index revealed very low cognitive and physical workload (average: 1.5). Participants experienced minimal stress and effort, supported by structured step-by-step guidance and a relaxed evaluation pace. The smartwatch-based stress monitoring solution was rated as completely non-intrusive (5). These scores are presented for each dimension in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Industrial adoption scores

Pilot components analysis

The pilot-specific evaluation results indicate a very positive overall perception of the XR-based training program and its associated components. The XR application demonstrated clear benefits for industrial support compared to traditional methods or systems in use, and it was perfectly aligned with the expectations from the participants. Satisfaction was also with the highest ranking (5). The participants agreed that development should continue toward large-scale deployment and that they foresee it becoming a widely used tool in the future.

Overall, results indicate strong acceptance and high perceived value across both junior and senior aircraft maintenance technicians (AMTs), despite the network connectivity constraints.

SECTION 5. CONCLUSIONS

The evaluation session provided important insights on the potential value of our XR-based training solution specifically designed for AMTs. Even though the limitations of the session, considering that it was not possible to test the real procedure in replacing the WAIV due to aircraft unavailability, the pilot session achieved its main goal of assessing user experience on the XR5.0 training for both use cases of the pilot. A key result of the pilot session was the setup and operation of the XR training infrastructure at TAP's shopfloor. The identified limitations were important to inform future deployment of this solution. The main limitation was related to the Wi-Fi connection that affected the streaming of the XR contents. The viable option was to run the standalone version with streaming from the Hololight streaming, but further tests and deployment will need to account for this issue.

Nevertheless, the overall results have suggested a promising and feasible solution that could be contributed to improve the effectiveness of the training for AMTs. Participants reported positive experiences in terms of system performance, visual quality, interaction, and ease of setup, suggesting that the technical foundation of the solution is achieving a good maturity level for training use cases.

From a training perspective, both use cases allowed participants to interact with the XR environment and explore training content related to the WAIV. The ability to navigate 3D models, follow workflows, and access information through multiple panels was evaluated as particularly useful. The evaluation of individual components also suggested the overall positive evaluation. The feedback gathered during this session will be important for further developing the app and the minor usability issues reported may contribute to design an anchoring system for the panels used in the XR training environments.

The lack of real equipment limited objective KPI measurement as it was not possible to assess skills training in the real environment, but the overall results are promising and highlight the perceived value of the XR for AMT training. These findings will inform the further development steps and deployment of these solutions in real operational environments.

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